

TKM9

P. Vivekanandan, J. Venkatakrishnan, K. N. Pillai, and D. S. Aaron, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur, Tamil Nadu, India

TKM9 has short bold, red unscented grains. Amylose content is 25% with low gelatinization temperature and high alkali digestion. The variety has some sheath blight resistance.

In 1982, TKM9 was entered in the International Testing Program trials to test its performance in the International Rice Yield Nursery very early

Table 1. TKM9 performance in international yield trials, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Av yield (t/ha)	Av days to flowering
IR50	4.9	86
IR9729-67-3	4.8	80
TKM9	4.6	84
BG367-7	4.6	84

group. It was evaluated with 25 elite breeding lines and IR50 (international check) at 22 sites in 11 countries. TKM9 yielded an average 4.6 t/ha and ranked third following IR50 and IR9729-67-3 (Table 1).

Table 2. TKM9 performance in India and Bangladesh.

Variety	Av yield (t/ha)	Av days to flowering
TKM9	4.6	82
BG367-7	4.4	80
IR15429-268-1-2-1	4.4	75
IR9729-67-3	4.4	76
IR50	4.4	82

At 8 sites in India and Bangladesh, TKM9 yielded better than IR50 with 4.6 t/ha (Table 2). IR9729-67-3, IR50, and TKM9 either produced the highest or were statistically equal to the highest yielders in more than 10 of 22 sites. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DISEASE RESISTANCE

Varieties with different resistance to tungro (RTV) and green leafhopper (GLH)

G. Dahal and H. Hibino, Plant Pathology Department, IRRI

We tested eight RTV-resistant varieties, with varying levels of resistance to vector GLH *Nephotettix virescens*, for reaction to rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) and their vector. TN1 was the susceptible check.

Reaction to GLH was evaluated by preference, percent nymphal survival, adult life span, and feeding site. Feeding site was determined by the color reaction of honeydew spots on filter paper treated with bromocresol green.

Reaction to viruses was determined by inoculating 1-wk-old seedlings with 1, 3, or 5 GLH from RTBV- and RTSV-infected TN1 plants. Seedling infection percentage was scored by visual observation and infected seedlings were tested by latex test using antisera 1 mo after inoculation.

Utri Merah, Utri Rajapan, and TN1 were preferred by GLH; the hoppers had high nymphal survival and long life span (Table 1). GLH preferred IR60, but had high mortality and short life span on that variety. ASD7 and ASD8 were least preferred and GLH on them had low nymphal

Table 1. Reaction of 9 rice varieties to GLH, IRRI.

	Preference	Nymph survival (%)	Average life span	Feeding site
Gam Pai 30-12-15	No	Low	Short	Xylem
ASD7	No	Low	Short	Xylem
ASD8	No	Low	Short	Xylem
Utri Merah	Yes	High	Longer	Xylem, phloem
Utri Rajapan	Yes	High	Longer	Xylem, phloem
IR50	No	Low	Short	Xylem
IR58	No	Low	Short	Xylem
IR60	Yes	Low	Short	Xylem
TN1	Yes	High	Longer	Xylem, phloem

Seedling infection (%)

Seedling infection percentage of 9 rice varieties inoculated in the test tube with 1, 3, or 5 GLH exposed to TN1 plants infected with RTBV and RTSV.